

FATIGUE TESTING OF CARBON FABRIC THERMOPLASTICS: DIFFERENT TESTING AND INSTRUMENTATION STRATEGIES

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SUMMARY

In this paper, the fatigue behaviour of carbon fabric reinforced thermoplastics has been studied. New experimental set-ups for fatigue testing have been designed and different instrumentation strategies have been explored.

In tension-tension fatigue, the carbon fabric reinforced thermoplastic shows hardly no stiffness degradation or accumulation of permanent strain, when tested in the warp or weft direction. Optical fibre sensors have been successfully embedded in the composite laminates. The electrical resistance method has also been applied to the carbon fabric thermoplastic.

Further, pure shear testing in fatigue was envisaged. A new set-up has been built for three-rail shear testing in fatigue. Finally, different bending set-ups were investigated. Because of the small thickness of the laminates, the midspan deflections were considerable during fatigue, and as a consequence geometric nonlinearity and friction at the supports could not be neglected in the simulations.

Keywords: fatigue, thermoplastic composites, bending, rail shear, instrumentation

INTRODUCTION

Fibre-reinforced thermoplastics are finding more and more applications in the aerospace industry for various parts and under various loading conditions. As such, a thorough understanding of their mechanical behaviour is needed.

This article presents different testing and instrumentation strategies for investigating the behaviour of a carbon fabric-reinforced thermoplastic under fatigue loading conditions.

The material used for the experiments was a 5-harness satin-weave carbon fabric-reinforced polyphenylene sulphide (PPS). The carbon PPS plates were hot pressed, one stacking sequence was used for this study, namely $[(0^\circ, 90^\circ)]_{4s}$ where $(0^\circ, 90^\circ)$ represents one layer of fabric. The in-plane elastic properties and the tensile strength properties are listed in Table 1. This material was supplied to us by Ten Cate Advanced Composites.

First, the use of (embedded) optical fibre gratings for longitudinal strain measurement is investigated, and electrical resistance measurement for damage characterization throughout the fatigue experiment will be commented on. Next, the in-plane shear behaviour of the material will be studied under fatigue loading conditions with a modified three-rail shear test setup. The latter is based on frictional and geometrical gripping and as such, there is no longer need for drilling holes through the specimen.

Table 1 Elastic and strength properties of the CETEX® material.

E_{11} [GPa]	56.0	X_T [MPa]	736
E_{22} [GPa]	57.0	ϵ_{11}^{ult} [-]	0.011
ν_{12} [-]	0.033	Y_T [MPa]	754.0
G_{12} [GPa]	4.175	ϵ_{22}^{ult} [-]	0.013
		S_T [MPa]	110.0

Finally, since realistic fatigue loading conditions often include bending loads, a discussion will be given on the pro's and con's of a bending setup for fatigue of thin composite laminates and a modified clamped three-point bending setup is presented.

OPTICAL FIBRE GRATINGS

The principle of an optical fibre sensor with a Bragg grating (FBG) is illustrated in Figure 1(a). Broadband light is transmitted into the optical fibre. At a specific point in this fibre, there is a Bragg grating, which acts as a wavelength selective mirror. For each grating only one wavelength, the Bragg wavelength, λ_B is reflected with a Full Width at Half Maximum of typically 100 pm, while all other wavelengths are transmitted. As a result, an optical fibre can be read out from both ends of the fibre.

These optical fibres were embedded in the carbon/PPS composite and several fatigue experiments were performed.

For the optical data acquisition, an SLI 100 was used, which has a samplerate of 100 Hz. However, this rate is too low to measure continuously during the fatigue experiments, so after a certain number of cycles, the fatigue test was paused for a displacement-controlled quasi-static test at 2 mm/min.

Figure 1(b) illustrates the measured strains, both with the extensometer as the optical fibre for these intermediate static tests of a fatigue experiment. The latter was done at 5 Hz between $\sigma=0$ MPa and $\sigma=300$ MPa in load-control. The strain is plotted as a function of time [s], the different curves are given a certain offset with respect to each other, to have a clear image. Underneath each measurement, the corresponding cycle is noted; the first curve corresponds with the initial static test.

The results correspond perfectly. The small plateau at the end of the optical measurement is due to the saturation of the optical data acquisition unit, it corresponds with a wavelength of 1560 nm. The extensometer measurement was stopped a little after the SLI saturated.

(a) Principle of the FBG

(b) Fatigue results

Figure 1 Optical fibre sensors.

ELECTRICAL RESISTANCE MEASUREMENT

Since carbon fibres conduct electricity, the electrical resistance of a carbon composite can be used to monitor (fibre) damage during fatigue loading. The more fibres are broken, the less conductive paths exist in the specimen and the higher the resistance becomes.

In order to have sensitive and time-stable signal, the four-probe method was used, meaning that two contacts are used to inject the current and two other contacts are used to measure the voltage (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Four-probe method.

The resistance is then calculated by dividing the voltage through the current. First, the principle is tested for a simple quasi-static test till failure at a speed of 2 mm/min. The results are given in Figure 3(a) and a clearly increasing resistance can be noted till failure.

Next, this technique was used to monitor a 5 Hz fatigue experiment. As can be seen in Figure 3(b), the resistance clearly follows the loading and unloading of the specimen, proving that the method works. Unfortunately, the material behaved very brittle, no stiffness degradation or permanent deformation occurred, meaning that the main damage mechanism of the material under study was not a gradual increase in broken fibres. As a result, there was no gradual increase in resistance throughout the fatigue life.

Figure 3 Electrical resistance measurements.

IN-PLANE SHEAR TESTING

If the in-plane shear behaviour of fibre-reinforced composites is studied, the three-rail shear test is almost never considered, although it can be an interesting test setup.

The standard setup requires drilling holes through the specimen, which should be avoided, especially in fatigue, since the holes may cause preliminary failure.

Therefore, a new design was made, based on frictional and geometrical gripping (Figure 4). As such, there is no need to drill holes through the specimen.

Figure 4 New design of a rail shear grip.

First, it was validated that this new design induced a symmetrical load and that no buckling of the specimen occurred. For this purpose, several quasi-static and hysteresis experiments were performed and it could be concluded that the grips induced a symmetrical load without buckling. Figure 5 (a) illustrates two quasi-static tests with the three-rail shear test. For comparison, a $[(+45^\circ, -45^\circ)]_{4s}$ tension test was also done to

verify the nonlinear behaviour and the shear stiffness. As can be seen, the results correspond very well.

Various fatigue experiments were performed to examine the behaviour of both the grips and the material under fatigue loading conditions. With respect to the grips, it could be concluded that they fulfil their purpose. With respect to the material under study, Figure 5 (b) illustrates the evolution of the temperature and the displacement during a load-controlled fatigue test between 0 and 45 MPa shear stress at 2 Hz. In general, the material behaviour can be described as follows: the carbon/PPS has an increase in permanent deformation and a decrease in shear stiffness until a certain point in time, after which a drastic increase in deformation and temperature occurs. The latter exceeds the softening temperature of the polyphenylene matrix. Also, the maximum value of the shear stress amplitude for fatigue with $R = 0$ as well as the loading frequency have a large influence on the fatigue lifetime.

Figure 5 Experiments with the modified three-rail shear test.

All fatigue results from the three-rail shear test were also compared with corresponding $[(+45^\circ, -45^\circ)]_{45}$ tests and a similar behaviour was found.

MODIFIED THREE-POINT BENDING

Although bending fatigue tests are not widely accepted as a standard, they are used a lot for research purposes. They do have some important advantages as well: (i) bending loads often occur in in-service loading conditions, (ii) there are no problems with buckling, compared to tension/compression fatigue, and (iii) the required forces are much smaller. To evaluate the stiffness degradation and damage growth in the fibre-reinforced laminate, the hysteresis loop of one loading cycle can be measured. In case of three- and four-point bending fatigue, the history of bending force versus midspan displacement is recorded. There are, however, some problems when the standard three-point bending setup is used for fatigue testing of thin composite laminates with low bending stiffness: (i) the occurring hysteresis is mainly due to friction on the supports (ii) the friction causes significant wear damage of the specimen (iii) the large midspan

displacement that can be reached, limits the test frequency and therefore increases test times. By clamping the ends of a specimen in the three-point bending setup (Figure 6), membrane stresses are introduced in the specimen, resulting in higher bending forces for lower midspan displacements in comparison with the standard three-point bending setup.

Figure 6 Clamped three-point bending.

As such, higher test frequencies are possible. Figure 7 (a) illustrates three quasi-static tests on the material under study. It can be seen that the results are very reproducible and that indeed high forces are achieved for low midspan displacements (for comparison, failure in a standard three-point bending test occurred for $F_{max} = 900$ N at $d_{max} = 17$ mm).

Figure 7 (b) shows the maximum, minimum and average value of the bending force for a displacement controlled fatigue test at 2 Hz with a displacement amplitude of 6 mm. A decreasing trend of the maximum force can be noted.

Figure 7 Experiments with the clamped three-point bending.

However, one issue remains to be solved. During fatigue testing, the specimen tends to slide a little in the grips. Further research is currently done on how to avoid the slipping in the grips, since this phenomenon certainly has an influence on the measurement.

CONCLUSIONS

There are various ways of conducting and monitoring fatigue experiments on carbon fibre-reinforced thermoplastics. This paper has presented:

- The use of optical fibre Bragg gratings for monitoring the strain during fatigue experiments, with good results.
- The electrical resistance measurement for monitoring damage. Unfortunately, the main damage mechanism is not a gradual increase in broken fibres, so no increase in resistance could be measured.
- A new three-rail shear setup, based on frictional and geometrical clamping, suited for in-plane shear fatigue loading conditions
- A clamped three-point bending setup, better suited for bending fatigue than the standard three-point bending setup.

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